

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

TwINSol-CECs International Conference on Environmental and Sustainable Research Solutions

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia,
June 5-6, 2025

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Dear colleagues,

It is a great pleasure to welcome you to the **International Conference on Environmental and Sustainable Research Solutions**, the final conference of the **TwINSol-CECs project**. We are honored to host this event organized here in Novi Sad, by the Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, bringing together a diverse and inspiring group of researchers, experts, and project partners, who share a common commitment to advancing scientific knowledge in support of a more sustainable future towards a toxic-free environment.

This event marks the culmination of the TwINSol-CECs project, which has, over the past years, contributed significantly to strengthening research capacities of the Faculty of Technology Novi Sad in domain of environmental research, enhancing the international cooperation of our researchers, and promoting innovative approaches in the field of Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs). Building on the success of the 1st and 2nd TwINSol-CECs Workshops held in 2022, and 2024, this final conference is envisioned as our most ambitious event, both in scope and in outreach.

As part of the conference, the **3rd TwINSol-CECs Workshop** is held with the aim of presenting the TwINSol-CECs project's infrastructure and research. This includes showcasing the technical resources acquired through the project, as well as the project research activities carried out at the Faculty of Technology Novi Sad. The workshop is also intended as a platform for networking and fostering new collaborations, while raising awareness about the capabilities and resources available at our institution for future joint scientific endeavors.

In this spirit of collaboration and knowledge sharing, we are proud to host a joint session with the FERTILEAVES project (HUSRB/23S/11/027, Interreg VI-A IPA Hungary–Serbia Programme), and its 2nd Workshop, recognizing the importance of amplifying the impact of both initiatives. This joint session reflects our shared dedication to addressing environmental and sustainable challenges, and gathers the oral presentations oriented towards biotechnology-driven research solutions. It also serves as a strategic step toward more effective dissemination of the project results and broader visibility of the achieved outcomes.

We hope the conference program is dynamic enough to inspire the exchange of research ideas, challenge established perspectives, and foster new collaborations in the pursuit of cleaner technologies, healthier ecosystems, and a resilient, sustainable future.

We thank all participants for joining this triple event, and we wish that it will be a productive and inspiring gathering of researchers with memorable and meaningful networking.

Co-Chairs

Prof. Zita Šereš, Dr. Jelena Živančev, and Prof. Nataša Đurišić Mladenović

PROGRAM

TwINSol-CECs International Conference on Environmental and Sustainable Research Solutions, June 5-7, 2025

with satellites

3rd TwINSol-CECs Workshop, June 5-6, 2025

**2nd FERTILEAVES Workshop “Sustainable Solutions Through Biotechnological Approaches”,
June 5, 2025**

Organized by

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad (FoTNS), Serbia

PROGRAM

Thursday, June 5, 2025

Venue: Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Vojvodina, Braće Popović 5, Novi Sad

9.30-10.30 Registration

10.30-10.45 Welcome and opening speeches by the Conference Co-Chairs,
Zita Šereš, Acting Dean, TwINSol-CECs Project Manager for Strategic Issues, FoTNS
Jelena Živančev, FERTILEAVES Coordinator, FoTNS
Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović, TwINSol-CECs Coordinator, FoTNS

TwINSol-CECs and FERTILEAVES Joint Session: Environmental and Sustainable Solutions Through Biotechnological Approaches

Session Chairs: Csaba Vágvölgyi and Jelena Živančev

Plenary lecture

10.45-11.15 Phytomicrobiome as the source of beneficial bacteria and fungi for the alleviation of drought stress in agricultural crops

László Kredics, Orsolya Kedves, Tamás Marik, Csaba Vágvölgyi

Department of Biotechnology and Microbiology, Faculty of Science and Informatics, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary

Oral presentations

11.15–11.30 Innovations in climate-resilient crop breeding

Aleksandra Radanović, Sandra Cvejić, Dragana Rajković, Boško Dedić, Biljana Kiprovska, Maja Tanasković, Miloš Krstić, Jelena Ovuka, Sonja Gvozdenac, Sonja Tančić-Živanov, Nemanja Čuk, Verica Zelić, Dušan Dunderski, Jelena Jocković, Milan Jocković, Milan Miroslavljević, Siniša Jocić, Goran Bekavac, Ana Marjanović-Jeromela, Ankica Kondić-Špika, Dragana Miladinović

Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, Novi Sad, Serbia

11.30-11.45 Sunflower under stress: sustainable breeding solutions for drought adaptation and nutrition quality improvement
Sandra Cvejić, Boško Dedić, Aleksandra Radanović, Nada Grahovac, Milan Jocković, Nemanja Čuk, Jelena Jocković, Sonja Gvozdenac, Srđan Bursać, Siniša Jocić, Dragana Miladinović, Vladimir Miklič
Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, Novi Sad, Serbia

11.45-12.00 Refreshments

Oral presentations

12.00-12.15 Development of biorational methods for seed protection during storage against biotic and abiotic stressors
Sonja Gvozdenac¹, Jelena Ovuka¹, Miloš Krstić¹, Aleksandra Ilić¹, Nevena Nagl¹, Dušan Stanislavljević¹, Aleksandra Nastasić¹, Vladimir Miklič¹, Milica Škorić¹, Dejan Prvulović², Radenka Kolarov², Snežana Tanasković³, Dušan Marković³, Zagorka Lozanov-Crvenković⁴
¹Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, Novi Sad, Serbia
²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Agriculture, Novi Sad, Serbia
³University of Kragujevac, Faculty of Agronomy, Čačak, Serbia
⁴University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Novi Sad, Serbia

12.15-12.30 Bioactive ecdysteroid analogues: cinnamate esters and *tert*-butyl oxime ethers with antitrypanosomal properties
Márton Háznagy¹, Máté Vágvölgyi¹, Gábor Girst¹, Sandhya R. Krishnan², Kaushavi Cholke², Jürg Gertsch², Attila Hunyadi^{1,3}
¹Institute of Pharmacognosy, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary
²Institute of Biochemistry and Molecular Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland
³Interdisciplinary Centre for Natural Products, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary

12.30-12.45 Protoflavonoids: Exploring the non-tumor-related bioactivities of a rare group of natural products
Máté Vágvölgyi¹, George Anis Al-Qassab¹, Gábor Girst¹, Gabriella Spengler², Attila Hunyadi^{1,3}
¹Institute of Pharmacognosy, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary
²Department of Medical Microbiology and Immunobiology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary
³Interdisciplinary Centre for Natural Products, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary

12.45-14.00 Lunch break

Oral presentations

14.00-14.15 Tracking Emerging Contaminants in Soil: Integrating pollutant analysis into FERTILEAVES pilot study
Dušan Rakić, Igor Antić, Maja Buljovčić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović, Jelena Živančev
University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

14.15-14.30 Innovative *Bacillus*-based technology for plant growth promotion and yield enhancement in sweet potato farming
Ádám Bordé-Pavlicz¹, Tamás Monostori², László Kredics¹, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović³, Jelena Živančev³, Csaba Vágvölgyi¹
¹Department of Biotechnology and Microbiology, Faculty of Science and Informatics, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary
²Institute of Plant Sciences and Environmental Protection, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Szeged, Hódmezővásárhely, Hungary
³University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

14.30-14.45 The potential of digestate- and *Bacillus*-based circular soil amendment to enhance early tomato development,
Tatjana D. Dujković, Ivana S. Danilov, Vanja R. Vlajkov, Jovana A. Grahovac
University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Novi Sad, Serbia

14.45-15.00 Coffee break

**TwINSol-CECs Session: Environmental Research Solutions
Session Chairs: *Marinella Farre and Zita Šereš***

Plenary lecture

15.00-15.30 From data to action: advancing water treatment and monitoring with AI
Claudia F. Galinha
LAQV-REQUIMTE, Chemistry Department, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Caparica, Portugal

Invited lectures

15.30-15.50 Degradation of bioplastics and related compounds in a conventional WWTP process by activated sludge
Marta Llorca¹, David Alcaide-Benavides^{1,2}, Eloy Torres¹, Marinella Farré¹
¹ON HEALTH Research Group, Environmental Chemistry Department, IDAEA-CSIC, Barcelona, Spain
²Doctoral Programa in Analytical Chemistry and Environmental Science, Dep. Of Chemical Engineering and Analytical Chemistry, University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain

15.50-16.10 Embracing circular economy principles in wastewater treatment: by-products from the food industry as effective biosorbents for pollutant removal
Natalija Velić¹, Marija Stjepanović¹, Marta Ostojčić¹, Darko Velić¹, Janez Gorenšek², Sandra, Budžaki¹
¹University of Osijek, Faculty of Food Technology Osijek, Osijek, Croatia
² IAMB-Institute for Applied Mycology and Biotechnology, Celje, Slovenia

13.00-17.00 3rd TwINSol-CECs Workshop - TwINSol-CECs capacities and results - interactive session with project teams

Due to the relocation of the event from Faculty of Technology Novi Sad to the Vojvodina Chamber of Commerce and Industry, visits to the TwINSol-CECs laboratories will be replaced by a dedicated interactive session where participants can meet the research teams, discuss the capacities of the laboratories in front of the poster presentations on the equipment and project research activities.

Friday, June 6, 2025

Venue: Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Vojvodina, Braće Popović 5, Novi Sad

- 10.30-11.00 Registration
- 11.00-13.30 **Joint poster session of the TwINSol-CECs Conference and the 3rd TwINSol-CECs Workshop**
(set-up Friday, June 6, 10.30-11.00, dismantling on Friday, June 6, 16.30-17.00, or Saturday, June 7, 12.45-13.30)
- 13.30-14.30 Lunch break

TwINSol-CECs Session: Environmental Research Solutions
Session Chairs: Marta Llorca and Igor Antić

Plenary lecture

- 14.30-15.00 Micro- and nanoplastics: from the environment to humans
Marinella Farré, David Alcaide, Eloy Torres, Xavier Borrell, and Marta Llorca
On-Health Research group, Institute of Environmental Assessment and Water Research (IDAEA), CSIC, C. Jordi Girona, 18-26, Barcelona, 08034, Spain

Invited lecture

- 15.00-15.20 Wide-scope screening of emerging contaminants and their transformation products in wastewaters by using liquid chromatography high-resolution mass spectrometry
Dimitra A. Lambropoulou^{1,2}
¹Department of Chemistry, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece
²Centre for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation (CIRI-AUTH), Balkan Center, Thessaloniki, Greece

- 15.20-15.35 Coffee break

Invited lecture

- 15.35-15.55 PFAS from useful chemicals to environmental hot topic - solving the (bio)degradation puzzle
Vladimir Beškoski
University of Belgrade – Faculty of Chemistry, Belgrade, Serbia

Oral presentations

- 15.55-16.10 Passive but promising: passive sampling of per- and polyfluoroalkyl acids (PFAAS) in wastewater
Kristina Mraz¹, Antonin Halek ¹, Veronika Svobodova ¹, Vaclav Janda ¹, Jana Pulkrabova ¹, Jakub Hejnic ², Martin Srb ², Darina Dvorakova ¹, Vojtech Kouba ¹
¹ University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Prague, Czech Republic
² Prague Water Supply and Sewerage Company, Prague, Czech Republic
- 16.10-16.25 Mitigating transport of ionizable organic pollutants in alluvial soils using biochar
Tamara B. Apostolović¹, Marijana M. Kragulj Isakovski¹, Marko D. Šolić¹, Jelena M. Beljin¹, Irina B. Jevrosimov¹, Snežana P. Maletić¹
¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Novi Sad, Serbia

- 16.25-16.40 Biomonitoring of non-occupational arsenic exposure among advanced lung cancer patients in Vojvodina
Nataša Milošević¹, Danica Szadanić-Velikić², Mirjana Ševo^{3,4}, Danijela Lukić⁵, Maja Milanović¹, Nataša Milić¹
¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Novi Sad, Serbia
²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina, Clinic for Pulmonary Oncology, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia
³University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia
⁴IMC Banja Luka-Center of Radiotherapy, Part of Affidea Group, Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina
⁵Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

- 13.30-17.00 **3rd TwINSol-CECs Workshop - TwINSol-CECs capacities and results - interactive session with project teams**

Saturday, June 7, 2025

Venue: Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Vojvodina, Braće Popović 5, Novi Sad

- 9.30-10.00 Registration

Session: Environmental Research Solutions

Session Chairs: Claudia Galinha and Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović

Keynote lecture

- 10.00-10.45 Confronting the threat of TFA and other persistent and mobile substances to protect water resources
Hans Peter H. Arp^{1,2}
¹ Norwegian Geotechnical Institute (NGI), Oslo, Norway,
² Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Trondheim, Norway

Invited lecture

- 10.45-11.05 Carbon based amendments advancing sustainable solutions for contaminated environmental matrices
Snežana Maletić, Jelena Beljin, Irina Jevrosimov, Tamara Apostolović, Srđan Rončević, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski
University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Novi Sad, Serbia

- 11.05-11.20 Coffee break

Oral presentations

- 11.20-11.35 Comparative life cycle assessment of sewage sludge management options in Serbia
Ferenc E. Kiss¹, Djurdja V. Kerkez², Milena R. Bečelić-Tomin², Anita S. Leovac Maćerak², Vesna Ž. Pešić²
¹ University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia
² University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia
- 11.35-11.50 UV/Chlorine process for degradation of Ibuprofen and Trimethoprim in aqueous solutions
Anett Čović, Luca Farkas, Teodóra Dragić and Tünde Alapi
Department of Molecular and Analytical Chemistry, University of Szeged, Hungary

INVITED LECTURE

CARBON BASED AMENDMENTS ADVANCING SUSTAINABLE SOLUTIONS FOR CONTAMINATED ENVIRONMENTAL MATRICES

***Snežana Maletić**, Jelena Beljin, Irina Jevrosimov, Tamara Apostolović, Srđan Rončević, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski**

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia,

**snezana.maletic@dh.uns.ac.rs*

Contaminated environmental matrices, including soils and sediments, present ongoing challenges to ecosystem integrity, human health, and sustainable land and water management. This research offers a detailed investigation into the potential of organic and carbon-based amendments, such as biochar, hydrochar, and compost-derived materials, to mitigate the risks posed by a broad spectrum of organic pollutants. Laboratory-based studies demonstrate that these amendments enhance contaminant retention by improving sorption capacity and modifying physicochemical properties of the matrices. By reducing pollutant mobility and bioavailability, amendments decrease the likelihood of contaminants leaching into groundwater or uptake by organisms. Additionally, the amendments contribute to the stimulation of microbial communities that can biodegrade certain classes of organic contaminants, thereby supporting natural attenuation processes. Comparative analyses of different amendment types reveal that material properties, including surface area, porosity, and chemical composition, critically influence sorption effectiveness and pollutant stabilization. Moreover, the interaction mechanisms between amendments and pollutants involve a combination of hydrophobic partitioning, π - π interactions, and surface complexation, which collectively govern the fate and transport of contaminants in environmental matrices. These findings underscore the versatility of organic amendments as tailored remediation tools that can be optimized according to site-specific contamination profiles and environmental conditions. Incorporating such amendments aligns with sustainable remediation principles and circular bioeconomy goals by utilizing waste-derived materials to restore ecosystem function and reduce environmental risk. Overall, this body of work highlights the promising role of carbon based amendments in enhancing the safety and quality of contaminated environmental matrices, offering a foundation for future applied research and the development of nature-based remediation strategies.

Keywords: environmental remediation, organic amendments, contaminant bioaccessibility, contaminant sorption, biodegradation

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